

Polypropylene micro- and nanoplastics affect the digestion of cow's milk proteins in infant model of gastric digestion[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Infants may ingest large quantities of micro- and nanoplastics (MNP) due to the heating and sterilization of the feeding bottles, which promotes the generation and migration of MNP into the milk or milk formula. The effect of MNP on the digestion of proteins, which are crucial for the growth and development of infants remain unknown. The current study investigated the *in vitro* digestion of cow's milk proteins (1 mg/mL) with or without polypropylene (PP) microplastics (MP, pristine or oxidized) (20 mg/mL and 63–180 μm) in simulated gastric fluids (SGF) using an infant (pH 5.0; pepsin activity; 268 U/mL) or adult (pH 3.0; pepsin activity; 2000 U/mL) digestion model at 37 °C for 5, 30, and 120 min. Secondly, the effect of the presence of agglomerated PP nanoplastics (NP, 10, 50, and 100 μg/mL) in milk on the *in vitro* digestion process using the infant model of gastric digestion was investigated. The profiles of protein digestion products, soft corona and hard corona, were analyzed using SDS-PAGE, and nLC-MS/MS, respectively. Cow's milk protein digestion with or without PP-MP was significantly slower in the infant compared to the adult model, and oxidation of the PP-MP enriched some proteins in the soft and hard corona. In the presence of agglomerated PP-NP, an additional decrease in the rate of milk protein digestion was observed, especially proteins of Mw between 18 and 20 kDa, presumably allergenic β-lactoglobulin. Irrespective of the type of PP, six different types of proteins, including casein α-S1, α-S2, β and κ, β-lactoglobulin, and α-lactalbumin, were present both in the soft and hard corona. Our results indicate a direct impact of PP-MNP on the rate of milk protein digestion in the infant model of gastric digestion. Aging of PP MP through oxidation and smaller size nanoplastics exert more pronounced effects on the digestion of cow's milk proteins *in vitro*. This suggests that PP-MNP could affect the biological functions of milk proteins and promote chronic health problems.

1. Introduction

Plastics are an important part of our daily lives. Notwithstanding the convenience brought about by plastics to human lives, research has revealed that plastics can be broken down into microplastics (MP, size: <5 mm or between 1 μm and 5 mm) and nanoplastics (NP, size: <1 μm) through various mechanisms, enter the human body, and potentially cause health problems (Amran et al., 2022). Given their potential negative health effects, micro- and nanoplastics (MNP) have become a

global issue that has attracted the attention of various private and public institutions and organizations (Osman et al., 2023). The exposure of humans to MNP can occur through various pathways; however, the oral route is the most important route for foods and beverages contaminated with MNP (Borriello et al., 2023).

Foods are contaminated with MNP in numerous ways, which include through the food chain, during manufacturing, preparation, and migration from the plastic packaging (Osman et al., 2023). Evidence of the presence of MNP in foods and the human body continues to grow.

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MNP of diverse types, sizes, morphology, and concentration have been detected in foods such as drinking water, tea bags, sea food, salt, honey, sugar, and milk products (Borriello et al., 2023; Kaseke et al., 2023; Yoganandham et al., 2023; Sridhar et al., 2022; Bai et al., 2022). In addition, the literature has reported the presence of various types of MNP, including polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polystyrene (PS), polypropylene (PP), polyethylene (PE), and polyvinyl chloride (PVC), in human feces, further demonstrating that MNP might enter the human body via the diet and are transported through the digestive system (Yan et al., 2020; Schwabl et al., 2019). Despite the compelling evidence of the occurrence of MNP in the human body, knowledge on their effects on the digestion of nutrients, especially proteins, is inadequate.

Although the effect of MNP on human health is still controversial, multiple studies conducted using *in vitro* and *in vivo* models have suggested that MNP can lead to a variety of health problems in humans, including gastrointestinal disorders, obesity, inflammation, cardiovascular disease, disruption of the endocrine system, and damage to vital organs including the liver and spleen (Zhang et al., 2024; Feng et al., 2023; Fan et al., 2022; O'Neill and Lawler, 2021). Additionally, MNP could disrupt the digestion and bioavailability of important nutrients such as proteins, affecting the proper functioning of the human body, or triggering chronic health diseases. DeLoid et al. (2022) demonstrated that PE-MP depleted β -casein and caused the enrichment of triacylglycerol lipase in the intestinal digestion phase. Healthy adult zebra fish exposed to PS-MP showed considerable alteration of amino acids that included phenylalanine, proline, lysine, leucine, threonine, alanine, glutamine, tyrosine, and ornithine (Qiao et al., 2019). de Guzman et al. (2023) established that caseins from cow milk are present in the hard corona of PS-MP during gastric digestion of milk causing delayed digestion of larger peptides. In spite of this, the literature lacks information relating to the impact of MNP on the digestion and absorption of proteins, particularly in vulnerable age groups such as infants. Compared to MP, NP are more difficult to produce and characterize; therefore, their presence in foods and effect on nutrient digestion and metabolism have not received adequate attention from researchers, although they are perceived to have more detrimental health effects. Due to their small size, NP can more easily enter the bloodstream and have a higher likelihood of interacting with plasma proteins (Hollóczki and Gehrke, 2019).

Cow's milk is an excellent source of high-quality proteins and essential micronutrients, including vitamins and minerals (Antunes et al., 2022). Its protein is of high biological value, presenting all essential amino acids and exhibiting a high digestibility (Scholz-Ahrens et al., 2020). Cow's milk contains bioactive proteins such as lactoferrin, lysozyme, secretory immunoglobulin, lactalbumin, κ -casein, and β -casein, which increase the absorption of nutrients in the gastrointestinal tract and stimulate the immune system and defence mechanisms against pathogens (Sun et al., 2020). Consequently, most infant formula products contain cow's milk, making it an essential part of the diet of infants. Given the high concentrations of MNP reported in cow's milk and infants' daily milk consumption patterns, bottle-milk-fed infants are exposed to substantial amounts of MNP. The preparation process, which includes heat treatment to sterilize the feeding bottles, contributes to the increased presence of MNP in formula milk (Li et al., 2020). As reported in a previous study, infants could consume approximately 1.6 million MNP per day (Li et al., 2020). MNP from feed bottles were found to be six times higher than those from milk powders, and these high numbers of MNP were attributed to the formula milk preparation process and bottle cleaning (Zhang et al., 2024). Furthermore, prolonged use of the same plasticware in the preparation of milk formula, which is a common practice in infant feeding, may facilitate the aging of the MNP, affecting their physicochemical properties and interaction with plasma proteins (Wen et al., 2022). Considering the vulnerability of infants to MNP and the significance of proteins in infant growth and development, greater insights into the influence of MNP on the digestion of proteins in infants are warranted.

PP forms one of the primary types of plastics used to manufacture baby bottles and tableware, and contamination of prepared milk formula with PP-MP has been reported (Kaseke et al., 2023; Li et al., 2021; Li et al., 2020). However, information on the influence of PP-MNP on the digestion of proteins in infant simulated digestive fluids, such as the simulated gastric fluid, is not available in the literature. Understanding the effect of PP-MNP on the digestion and absorption of proteins in infants is necessary to provide precise data that may be used to guide the development of standards or regulations that control PP-MNP in different types of foods. Given the diversity of PP-MNP consumers may ingest and their potential health effects, the study described herein sought to investigate the effect of PP-MNP and oxidized PP-MP on the *in vitro* digestion of cow's milk proteins in simulated gastric fluids using the infant digestion model. Even though the physicochemical alterations of aged MP can significantly enhance the interaction of MP with proteins, the literature is deficient of studies addressing the role of MP aging in protein digestion.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials and chemicals

2.1.1. Defatted milk preparation

Pasteurized skimmed cow's milk (1 % fat) (Imlek brand, Serbia) was purchased from a local supermarket in Belgrade, Serbia. The milk was further defatted by centrifugation at $4000\times g$ and $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 30 min using the Eppendorf Centrifuge 5804R (Kumberg, Austria). The final fat (0.7 %) and protein content (31.36 mg/mL) of the milk were determined using the gravimetric method and the bicinchoninic acid (BCA) method, respectively (Section S1).

2.1.2. PP-MP and PP-NP production

PP-MP (63–100 μm) powder both oxidized and pristine were produced according to the procedures described in Section S2. An ethanolic suspension of PP-NP (14.57 mg/mL) were produced according to the recently published protocol (Wimmer et al., 2025) and briefly described in Section S3.

2.2. Characterisation of PP-MP and PP-NP

Before use in the simulated *in vitro* digestion experiments, the PP-MP and PP-NP were characterized according to size distribution, shape and identity using a Mastersizer 3000 laser diffraction particle size analyzer (Malvern Panalytical, Malvern, United Kingdom), ECHO Revolve microscope (BICO group, Goteborg, Sweden) and Nicolet iN10 MX Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Frankfurt, Germany), respectively. The detailed procedures are provided in Section S4. In a previous study, we have shown that PP-NP produced are roughly spherical. Based on scanning electron microscopy (SEM) imaging, no primary particles above 1 μm were detected (Wimmer et al., 2025).

2.3. Static *in vitro* gastric digestion of cow's milk proteins using infant and adult digestion models

The simulated *in vitro* digestion of cow's milk proteins using the adult and infant models was performed according to the Infogest 2.0 protocol (Brodkorb et al., 2019), with minor modifications for the infant digestion model. These modifications were necessary to mimic the infant gastrointestinal conditions and included changes in pH and pepsin activity in which the simulated gastric fluid (SGF) pH 5 and pepsin activity of 268 IU/mL were used instead of SGF pH 3 and pepsin activity of 2000 IU/mL for the adult model (Elwakiel et al., 2020). The pepsin enzyme from porcine gastric mucosa (P7000-25G) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany). The specific activity of the pepsin enzyme (481 U/mg) was determined according to the INFOGEST protocol in

which haemoglobin was used as the substrate (Brodkorb et al., 2019). Other chemicals used in this study including those used to prepare the simulated digestion fluids were of analytical grade. The simulated digestion fluids that included simulated salivary fluid (SSF, pH 7) and SGF (pH 3 or 5) were prepared according to Tables S1 and S2.

2.3.1. Digestion of cow's milk proteins with or without PP-MP using infant and adult digestion models

The mixture for the digestion of cow's milk proteins using either the infant or adult digestion model was prepared according to Table S3. Briefly, 20 mg of PP-MP pristine (for both models) or oxidized (infant model only) was mixed with 32 μ L of the defatted cow's milk diluted with SSF in 1.5 mL glass vials to mimic the passage of milk in the gastrointestinal tract. Then, 500 μ L of pepsin (activity 536 or 4000 U/mL dissolved in SGF pH 5 or 3, respectively) and an appropriate volume of 0.5 M HCl were added to maintain the required pH for each model. The concentration of cow's milk protein and activity of pepsin enzyme in the final reaction mixture was 1 mg/mL and 268 or 2000 U/mL, respectively. In addition, two controls were prepared; the first control contained only cow's milk and pepsin enzyme, while the second control contained PP-MP and pepsin enzyme (Table S3). No gastric lipase was added because the skimmed cow's milk was additionally defatted and contained 0.7 % fat. The prepared mixture was then placed in a shaking incubator (New Brunswick, Innova 42 incubator shaker, Canada) at 37 °C to allow digestion for 5, 30, and 120 min. For the oxidized PP-MP the selected time of digestion was 30 min. The changes in protein profiles during digestion were compared to the protein profiles in cow's milk diluted with Milli-Q water (1 mg/mL) and incubated under the same conditions (denoted by M) (Table S3). After digestion, the pepsin enzyme was inactivated by adjusting the pH of the digestion mixture to pH 7–8 using an appropriate volume of 0.5 M sodium carbonate (Table S3). The mixture was centrifuged for 2 min at 1000 \times g, after which the liquid from the mixture was separated from the PP-MP using a syringe and transferred to Eppendorf tubes.

2.3.2. Digestion of cow's milk proteins with or without PP-NP using an infant digestion model

The digestion of cow's milk proteins in the presence of PP-NP was performed using the infant model only (Table S4). In short, the PP-NP (14.57 mg/mL) suspended in ethanol was thoroughly vortexed, then the calculated volume of the suspension was transferred into 1.5 mL vials, and the excess ethanol was evaporated at 37 °C. SSF (pH 7) was added to achieve the desired final PP-NP concentrations of 10, 50, and 100 μ g/mL. The diluted PP-NP was then mixed with milk, pepsin solution and 0.5 M HCl as shown in Table S4. Further steps of digestion were the same as in Section 2.3.1 except the duration of digestion. In this experiment, 30 min of digestion was selected based on the results obtained from the digestion of cow's milk in the presence of PP-MP. The range of PP-NP final concentrations were selected using estimates of MP quantities (4.1 μ g/week–5g/week) ingested by humans reported in the literature (Pletz, 2022; Mohamed Nor et al., 2021; Senathirajah et al., 2021). Both highest and median estimates were taken into account, as well as stomach capacity. Details of the calculated estimated MNP concentrations are shown in Supplementary, Section S5 and Table S5. Due to the small quantities and particle size of PP-NP in the mixture it was impossible to separate them from liquid, so their effect on the digestion of cow's milk proteins was investigated in bulk samples.

2.4. Extraction of soft and hard corona proteins from PP-MP

To analyze the change in profiles of proteins in the soft and hard corona during digestion, the next step was the extraction of proteins from the surface of the plastics. To the separated PP-MP (Section 2.3.1), 200 μ L of SGF was added, and the sample was vortexed for 15 s and then centrifuged at 1000 \times g for 2 min to extract the soft corona proteins (weakly bound proteins). This process was done three times to ensure

that all the soft corona proteins were extracted from the PP-MP and the fractions were denoted by SC1, SC2, and SC3. The proteins from the hard corona (strongly bound proteins) were extracted with 200 μ L of 1 time sample buffer for SDS-PAGE (0.2 mM Tris-HCl buffer, pH 6.8, 40 % glycerol, 2 % SDS, 0.04 % bromophenol blue, and β -mercaptoethanol (19:1, v/v)) diluted with Milli-Q water, vortexed for 30 s, and centrifuged at 1000 \times g for 2 min.

2.5. Analysis of protein profiles during digestion using SDS-PAGE

Bulk solutions obtained during the digestion of cow's milk with and without PP-MP (pristine and oxidized), PP-NP, as well as the extracts of soft and hard corona proteins, were mixed with appropriate volumes of 5-times concentrated sample buffer for SDS-PAGE. After heating at 95 °C for 10 min, the samples were stored at –20 °C until further analysis. For the analysis of protein profiles, the Sodium dodecyl-sulfate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) 1D was employed (Bio-Rad Mini-PROTEAN system, Bio-Rad laboratories, California, USA), following the manufacturer's protocol. The samples (15 μ L) and protein markers (14.4–116 kDa) (7 μ L) were loaded into a 14 % resolving gel (Table S6) and run according to Laemmli (1970). After electrophoresis, the gels were fixed, stained with 0.05 % w/v Coomassie brilliant blue R-250 and then destained. The destained gels were then scanned using the Typhoon FLA 7000 laser scanner (GE Healthcare Biosciences AB, Uppsala, Sweden). Bands of selected proteins on SDS-PAGE gels were quantified by densitometry using the ImageJ software 1.54d (National Institute of Health, USA) to analyze their changes during digestion (Section S6).

2.6. Protein identification using nano-scale liquid chromatographic tandem mass spectrometry (nLC-MS/MS)

The identification of proteins in the bands of interest (Fig. S1) obtained after SDS-PAGE of samples subjected to digestion using the infant model of digestion of cow's milk with PP-MP (oxidized and pristine) and PP-NP were carefully excised from the gels and analyzed using a nLC-MS/MS (de Guzman et al., 2023). The experiment was repeated twice.

2.6.1. Trypsin digestion

The selected peptide bands were firstly digested with trypsin (Sigma-Aldrich) according to a protocol described by Shevchenko et al. (2006) (Section S7). Other chemicals used that included ammonium bicarbonate, acetonitrile, iodoacetamide, and formic acid were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich.

2.6.2. Separation and identification of peptides

The separation of in-gel digested proteins was performed using the UltiMate™ 3000 RSLC nano-Liquid Chromatographic System (Thermo Scientific Inc., Bremen, Germany) coupled with Orbitrap Exploris 240 mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Bremen, Germany) equipped with heated electrospray ionization source. Peptide identification was performed using PEAKS Suite XPro (Bioinformatics Solutions Inc., Canada) The mass spectrometry proteomics data was deposited to the ProteomeXchange Consortium via the PRIDE [1] partner repository with the dataset identifier PXD057063 and 10.6019/PXD057063 (Section S7).

2.7. Statistical analysis

The data for particle size distribution and protein concentration for specific peptide bands, which is presented as mean \pm standard error (SE) was analyzed using the STATISTICA software v 14.0.0.15 (TIBCO Software Inc, California, USA). The means for protein concentration were separated using the Duncan's multiple-range test at a 5 % significance level.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of PP-MNP

3.1.1. Particle size distribution of PP-MP

The volume-based particle size distribution of the milled and sieved PP-MP varied between 45 and 165 μm . The 10th, 50th (median), and 90th percentile of the particle size distribution curve (Dv 10, Dv 50, Dv 90) were 45, 92, and 165 μm , respectively. These particles exhibited non-spherical shapes and irregular surfaces, due to the milling of PP pellets (Fig. 1a).

3.1.2. Particle size distribution of PP-NP, milk and their mixture

The particle size distribution of PP-NP obtained by precipitation into ethanol was between 0.13 and 0.48 μm (Fig. S2), confirming that all primary particles were in the submicron size range. When PP-NP were subsequently suspended in simulated digestive fluids aggregates formed with sizes ranging from roughly 10–100 μm , including the presence of a fraction of even larger aggregates (Fig. S2). Therefore, we refer to these test systems as agglomerated PP-NP, the bulk of which exhibited a size range (\sim 10–100 μm) roughly comparable to the milled PP-MP. Agglomeration of PP in SGF was also observed by Stock et al. (2020). Therefore, it can be assumed that mixing hydrophobic plastic particles

with SGF fosters particle aggregation and presents a challenge in measuring their size distribution. The milk particle size varied between 0.17 μm and 130 μm (Fig. S2), a size range that corresponded to the size of casein micelles (20–600 nm) (Bijl et al., 2014; Jhanwar and Ward, 2014). The larger particles observed in the cow's milk could indicate some precipitation, given that pH 5 is close to the isoelectric point of caseins (Post et al., 2012). Subsequent dilution of PP-NP in simulated fluids with milk did not appear to substantially alter the particle size distribution of the aggregates (Fig. 1b). The agglomeration of the PP-NP in our test system did not invalidate our study aims and hypotheses, since nanoplastics are reported to be present in aggregated form in the environment (Pradel et al., 2023). Secondly, the milled PP-MP and the agglomerated PP-NP are hypothesized to exhibit different surface properties, which may influence their effects on digestion.

3.1.3. Micro-FTIR analysis of oxidized and pristine PP-MP

Prolonged use of PP-based plastic feeding bottles accompanied by constant heating in the presence of air might promote the aging of plastic and cause chemical and physical changes. In this respect, the chemical characteristics of oxidized and pristine PP-MP were compared (Fig. 2). According to the results, strong absorption peaks were observed around 2912 cm^{-1} and 2839 cm^{-1} , indicating the presence of C-H stretching vibrations that showed a higher absorbance signal in the

Fig. 1. Polypropylene particle size distribution and microscopic image (a) Microscopic image of polypropylene microplastics (PP-MP, 63–100 μm) (scale bar: 370 μm) and particles distribution suspended in diluted 5 % Tween 80 (b) Polypropylene nanoplastics (PP-NP) and milk particles distribution suspended in simulated fluids (SF) (simulated salivary fluid, SSF and simulated gastric fluid, SGF) at pH 5. Values for particle size distribution [Dv 10, 50 and 90 (μm)] represent the mean \pm SE (n = 3).

Fig. 2. Micro-FTIR spectra of (a) pristine and (b) oxidized polypropylene microplastics (PP-MP, 63–100 μm).

oxidized PP-MP. The peaks around 2350 cm^{-1} showing a higher absorbance signal in oxidized PP-MP suggest the presence of additional functional groups resulting from the oxidation process (Toapanta et al., 2021). The spectra in the fingerprint region of 1455 cm^{-1} and 1374 cm^{-1} , corresponding to C-H deformation, did not significantly differ between the oxidized and pristine plastics. These peaks are typical for PP and did not significantly change after oxidation. However, new peaks between 1500 cm^{-1} and 1700 cm^{-1} appeared in oxidized PP-MP which represents carbonyl groups (C=O), which exist in ketones, aldehydes, and anhydrides as a result of the oxidation of plastic polymers (Campanale et al., 2023; Khoironi et al., 2020). Furthermore, these structural changes in plastics could increase the adsorption of protein molecules on their surfaces (Du et al., 2023; Wen et al., 2022). These results imply that a more significant change in chemical structures of PP could occur with prolonged heating, suggesting that the changes could be even more pronounced in a real environmental sample.

3.2. Gastric digestion of milk proteins using infant and adult digestion models

Given the differences in the physiological conditions between infants and adults, that include differences in the gastric pH and activity of pepsin, the first goal of this study was to compare the gastric digestion of cow's milk proteins using infant and adult models. Proteolysis of cow's milk was observed using the SDS-PAGE of digested samples collected at different times (5, 30, and 120 min) and compared to undigested milk.

As illustrated in Fig. 3a, the progression of protein digestion significantly varied between infants and adults, with the infant digestion occurring at a relatively slower rate. Similar observations were reported in literature (Ménard et al., 2018; Dupont et al., 2010). Studies have shown that variations in pH and pepsin activity influence the digestion of food proteins, influencing the specificity, rate, and extent of proteolysis (Gan et al., 2018; Ménard et al., 2018). However, the differences observed in the present study could be due to a higher pH in infants (5.0) compared to adults (3.0) rather than the reduced pepsin activity. This is

Fig. 3. Protein profiles after gastric simulated digestion of milk with or without polypropylene microplastics (PP-MP, 63–100 μm) for 5, 30, and 120 min using the infant and adult digestion models (a) digestion of milk only, (b) digestion of milk in the presence of polypropylene microplastics, (c) soft corona, (d) hard corona. The figures show representative results of two separate experiments with similar results. The abbreviation Std stands for protein marker (kDa), and M for milk.

in accordance with the study of Dupont et al. (2010), which proved that pH had a more important effect than varying the pepsin enzyme activity on the digestion of β -casein and β -lactoglobulin using both models. This is further supported by the fact that protein structure is more sensitive to pH changes than enzyme activity alone (Zhang et al., 2024).

Distinct bands of peptides with molecular weights (MW) ranging from 25 to 35 kDa and corresponding to caseins were observed only in infants at 5 and 30 min time points, while in adults they were completely invisible. These bands of peptides were not visible after 120 min of the cow's milk digestion, indicating increased digestion of these peptides with pepsin over time, and this is in line with the literature (Chen et al., 2024; Ménard et al., 2018). Bands corresponding to peptides with MW varying between 14 and 20 kDa and likely to represent whey proteins were observed in all the digestion time points in infants but decreased in intensity with prolonged digestion, while in adults they were almost invisible with the same intensity of bands in all time points (Fig. 3a). The observation that these bands were still visible after 120 min of digestion in infants suggests that these peptides could be resistant to digestion. This has been extensively reported in the literature for the *in vitro* digestion of cow or human milk (de Guzman et al., 2023; Hodgkinson et al., 2018; Ménard et al., 2018; de Oliveira et al., 2017; Bourlieu et al., 2015; Dupont et al., 2010). Caseins have a more loose and flexible structure which makes them more easily digested by pepsin than whey proteins, which characterized by a globular and compact structure (Ménard et al., 2018). In addition, bands of peptides with MW less than 14 kDa were observed in all the studied digestion times in infants but became more intense with prolonged digestion, indicating the accumulation of smaller peptides due to further digestion of larger peptides (Fig. 3a).

3.3. Influence of PP-MP on the gastric digestion of milk proteins using infant and adult digestion models

The subsequent step investigated the influence of PP-MP on the digestion of milk proteins using both models. This study presents unprecedented results for the effect of PP-MP on the digestion of cow's milk proteins in infants. The addition of PP-MP to cow's milk considerably affected the digestion of proteins in infants, while no effect of PP-MP was observed in adults, possibly due to the increased rate of protein digestion in adults. This protein digestion impairment in infants can contribute to several health issues, such as poor weight gain, malnutrition, and an increased risk of allergies (Sabari et al., 2023). As depicted in Fig. 3b, the addition of PP-MP further slowed the digestion of proteins in infants, especially caseins. After 30 min of digestion, bands of caseins were more intense compared to bands obtained when milk was digested alone (Fig. 3a). This resulted in a 3-fold reduction in the digestion rate of caseins in the presence of PP-MP (Table 1). Even after 120 min of digestion in infants, bands of caseins were still visible, while the same bands of proteins completely disappeared in adults at all time points. Further, bands of whey proteins were observed at all time points of digestion in infants, but intensities of some of the bands were less dense than those from milk digested in the absence of plastics, demonstrating that the presence of PP-MP could change the rate of digestion of some proteins. The exact mechanism by which the PP-MP changes the digestion rate of milk proteins in infants remains unclear. However, *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies have suggested that MP bind to enzymes and cause conformational changes that could alter their activity (Polo et al., 2024; de Guzman et al., 2023; Frank et al., 2023). Nonetheless, the influence of MP on enzymes might vary with the origin and type of enzyme and the characteristics of MP (particle size, type, shape, and concentration) (Polo et al., 2024), highlighting the complexity of the interaction between enzymes and MP.

Table 1

Protein concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$) for specific peptide bands obtained after *in vitro* digestion of cow's milk, with and without the presence of plastics (PP-MP and agglomerated PP-NP), using an infant digestion model.

	Milk digested with or without PP-MP							
	Milk		5 min		30 min		120 min	
	25–35 kDa	14–20 kDa	25–35 kDa	14–20 kDa	25–35 kDa	14–20 kDa	25–35 kDa	14–20 kDa
Digestion of milk only	0.71 ±	0.28 ± 0.14 ^b	0.29 ± 0.01 ^b	0.15 ± 0.01 ^c	0.08 ± 0.01 ^d	0.11 ± 0.02 ^{cd}	–	0.08 ± 0.02 ^{cd}
Digestion of milk in the presence of PP-MP	0.18 ^a		0.24 ± 0.01 ^{bc}	0.11 ± 0.01 ^d	0.20 ± 0.00 ^c	0.10 ± 0.00 ^{de}	0.02 ± 0.01 ^f	0.06 ± 0.01 ^{ef}
Soft corona			0.28 ± 0.10 ^b	0.15 ± 0.02 ^{cd}	0.25 ± 0.06 ^b	0.20 ± 0.04 ^{bc}	0.08 ± 0.04 ^d	0.11 ± 0.02 ^{cd}
Hard corona			0.19 ± 0.09 ^{bc}	0.11 ± 0.08 ^c	0.30 ± 0.13 ^b	0.17 ± 0.07 ^{bc}	0.20 ± 0.11 ^{bc}	0.12 ± 0.08 ^c
	Milk digested in the presence of pristine or oxidized PP-MP for 30 min							
			Bulk		Soft corona		Hard corona	
Pristine	0.65 ±	0.17 ± 0.01 ^d	0.10 ± 0.02 ^c	0.07 ± 0.02 ^{cd}	0.01 ± 0.00 ^e	0.04 ± 0.01 ^{de}	0.18 ± 0.02 ^b	0.07 ± 0.01 ^{cd}
Oxidized	0.09 ^a		0.20 ± 0.03 ^d	0.21 ± 0.01 ^{cd}	0.03 ± 0.00 ^e	0.15 ± 0.03 ^d	0.43 ± 0.05 ^b	0.27 ± 0.02 ^c
	Milk digested in the presence of different concentrations of agglomerated PP-NP for 30 min							
			10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$		50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$		100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	
Bulk solution	0.72 ± 0.02 ^a	0.20 ± 0.01 ^c	0.04 ± 0.01 ^d	0.36 ± 0.05 ^b	0.08 ± 0.00 ^{cd}	0.45 ± 0.09 ^b	0.05 ± 0.00 ^d	0.47 ± 0.11 ^b

PP-MP = polypropylene microplastics, PP-NP = polypropylene nanoplastics. The data shown are the mean \pm SE of two separate experiments. Each column with values assigned different superscript letters are significantly different ($p < 0.05$) according to the Duncan's multiple range tests.

3.4. Effect of infant and adult digestion models on the formation of soft and hard protein coronas on PP-MP

To comprehensively understand the possible reasons for the observed differences in the digestion of milk in the presence of PP-MP between infants and adults, the formation of protein coronas (hard and soft) around the PP-MP particles was studied (Fig. 3c and d).

Fig. 3c shows clear differences in the protein profiles of soft corona in infants and adults during digestion, suggesting a significant effect of the different digestion conditions on the formation of soft corona. Irrespective of the different digestion times, in adults no binding of proteins from milk, except for two pepsin bands, were observed. This is supported by the results from de Guzman et al. (2023) for the digestion of milk proteins in the presence of PS-MP beads.

The profiles, along with the quantity and intensity of certain casein and whey protein bands, showed an increase after 5 min of digestion. However, most of these bands diminished after 120 min. The soft corona is sustained by weak protein-to-protein interactions and could have dissociated with prolonged digestion (García-Álvarez and Vallet-Regí, 2021). Apart from the differences observed in caseins and whey proteins in the soft corona in both models, the same trend was observed with hard corona protein profiles (Fig. 3d). In infants, the number and intensity of bands (caseins) increased from 5 to 30 min of digestion, and even after 120 min, the bands were still visible with an estimated 0.20 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$ of the same proteins (Table 1). According to these results, we can conclude that the caseins had a greater affinity to bind to PP-MP due to their amphiphilic properties and random structure (Khatun et al., 2022), compared to the largely hydrophilic and compact whey proteins (Dissanayake and Vasiljevic, 2009). Hard corona formation may cause protein conformational changes, forming a strong binding interface with the different types of MP (PP, PS, PET) (Brouwer et al., 2024; Gligorjevic et al., 2024; Walkey and Chan, 2012). This may impact protein functionality by exposing the functional epitopes or misfolding, resulting in the loss of protein function (Walkey and Chan, 2012) or even induced protein toxicity (Brouwer et al., 2024). As expected, hydrophobic surfaces, such as those of PP-MP, cause greater conformational changes than hydrophilic surfaces (Nienhaus and Nienhaus, 2023).

Given that pepsin was used to digest the cow's milk proteins, the enzyme could be involved in the formation of coronas. Fig. 3 shows that the intensity of the pepsin band in the bulk and soft corona in adults was denser than that in infants with or without the presence of milk, while in the hard corona no differences were observed (Fig. S3b). The binding of

digestion enzymes to MP has been identified as one of the ways MP affect nutrient digestion through the alteration of their secondary structure (Tan et al., 2020). The loss of pepsin activity and that of other types of enzymes as a consequence of conformational changes due to binding to MP have been reported in the literature (de Guzman et al., 2023; Tretraill et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2020).

Despite the recent advances on protein corona formation studies, more research is still warranted to deeply understand the process of formation of soft and hard corona and their consequences on protein functionality. Although reports from the literature indicate that the binding of proteins to the soft corona may not have serious implications for their assimilation relative to the hard corona proteins, our results showed that the biological relevance and impact of soft corona proteins should also be investigated.

3.5. Influence of PP-MP oxidation on milk protein digestion and formation of coronas using the infant digestion model

In the present study, aging of the PP-MP was performed through oxidation by heating in the presence of air before the digestion with milk proteins using an infant digestion model, and it was compared with pristine PP-MP. Fig. 4a and b show that protein profiles of bulk, soft, and hard coronas were different between digestions in the presence of oxidized and pristine plastics. It can be clearly seen that oxidation enriched some proteins in soft and hard corona, like the isoforms of caseins with the lowest MW and some whey proteins between 14 and 20 kDa, which were denser than those from cow's milk digested in the presence of pristine PP-MP. Saudrais et al. (2024) observed adsorption of haemoglobin on the surfaces of heat- or irradiation-aged PE-MP and PP-MP, suggesting that the aging process altered the surface properties of these microplastics. Densitometric analysis revealed that the binding of whey proteins to oxidized PP-MP was more than three times that observed with pristine PP-MP (Table 1). This phenomenon can be explained by observed changes in the chemical and structural properties of oxidized PP-MP, such as the introduction of a carbonyl group during oxidation (Section 3.1.2). Moreover, due to oxidation, the surface polarity of plastics increases, which could have caused some hydrophilic proteins to also strongly bind to the oxidized PP-MP through polar bonds such as those from hydrogen.

Fig. 4. Protein profiles after gastric simulated digestion of milk in the presence of pristine or oxidized polypropylene microplastics (PP-MP, 63–100 μm) and of nano-polypropylene (PP-NP) using the infant model for 30 min (a) digestion in the presence of pristine PP-MP, and (b) digestion in the presence of oxidized PP-MP, (c) milk digestion in the presence of different concentrations of agglomerated PP-NP (10, 50, and 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), and (d) pepsin incubated in the presence of agglomerated PP-NP. The figures show representative results of two separate experiments with similar results. The abbreviation Std stands for protein marker (kDa), and M for milk, C-MP for digestion of milk only, while BK, SC1, SC2, SC3, HC, and P stands for bulk, soft corona 1, soft corona 2, soft corona 3, hard corona proteins, and pepsin respectively. The numbers 10, 50, and 100 are concentrations of PP-NP in $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

3.6. Impact of agglomerated PP-NP on the digestion of milk proteins using the infant digestion model

The effect of different concentrations of agglomerated PP-NP (10–100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) on the digestion of cow's milk proteins was investigated. As a result of the smaller quantities of agglomerated PP-NP used in this study, effective separation of plastics from the bulk solution and further analysis of proteins in the soft and hard was impossible.

According to Fig. 4c, agglomerated PP-NP showed a dose-dependent effect on the digestion of milk proteins. The 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ concentration showed the least effect on the digestion of proteins, exhibiting a protein profile similar to the profile obtained for the digestion of milk in the absence of PP-NP. When the concentration of agglomerated PP-NP increased, protein bands with a MW > 45 kDa and caseins appeared. Further, selected bands of whey proteins increased in intensity, especially bands at and immediately above 18.4 kDa, compared to the corresponding bands obtained when 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of PP-NP was added. This finding is corroborated by the densitometric analysis results of the protein bands presented in Table 1. When compared to the protein profiles obtained in the bulk mixture after 30 min of milk digestion in the presence of PP-MP (Fig. 3a) and agglomerated PP-NP (Fig. 4c), it can be seen that some whey proteins (10–20 kDa) remained undigested, even when the concentration of PP-NP in the digestion mixture was 200 times lower than the concentration of PP-MP (20 mg/mL). Since whey proteins contain various allergenic proteins such as β -lactoglobulin, the significant delay in their digestion and accumulation in the stomach may either contribute to or aggravate allergic reactions in infants (de Guzman et al., 2023). Also, as previously highlighted, interaction of the agglomerated PP-NP and proteins ultimately leads to the protein corona formation and conformational changes of protein secondary structure (Windheim et al., 2022). Hollóczy and Gehrke (2019) studied the

interaction between various NP and small peptides and observed an increase in the presence of α -helices and β -sheet-like structures, suggesting misfolding of the proteins. These misfolded proteins could have a weaker interaction with pepsin in the solution, and therefore, their digestion can be delayed.

With respect to pepsin, increasing the concentration of PP-NP did not affect the intensity of pepsin bands (Fig. 4d). These results correlate with those obtained using PP-MP where pepsin bands were only observed in the profiles from bulk solution without any binding to plastics under the infant digestion model conditions (Fig. 3a, b, and 3c).

3.7. Identification of milk proteins after *in vitro* digestion using the infant digestion model

A total of 32 bands from the bulk, soft, and hard corona samples of PP-MP (oxidized and pristine) and agglomerated PP-NP were subjected to nLC-MS/MS analysis, and their protein identities were established.

According to Fig. 5, only eight different types of proteins (α -S1, α -S2, β - and K-casein, β -lactoglobulin, α -lactalbumin, serum albumin, and lactadherin) were identified in the analyzed bands. As specified by the literature, 80 % of cow's milk proteins consist of α -S1 and α -S2-caseins, β -casein, and K-casein, with MW between 35 and 45 kDa (Miranda et al., 2020). Among them, α -S1 constitutes the highest proportion, accounting for 38 % of the total caseins. The remaining proportion of proteins (20 %) belongs to whey proteins, such as β -lactoglobulin, α -lactalbumin, immunoglobulins, and bovine serum albumin. The β -lactoglobulin (18.4 kDa) and α -lactalbumin (14.2 kDa) constitute the predominant whey proteins. The same profile of proteins was obtained in the current study. Proteins identified in bands 1–6 obtained after 5 min of milk digestion without PP-MP suggest that the majority of caseins and β -lactoglobulin proteins were digested into smaller peptides, similar to

Milk and pepsin

Band	kDa	Protein identified
1	32	α -S1-casein, α -S2-casein, β -lactoglobulin
2	30	β -casein, β -lactoglobulin, α -S1-casein, α -S2-casein
3	28	α -S1-casein, α -S2-casein
4	21	β -casein, β -lactoglobulin
5	18.5	β -lactoglobulin
6	13.5	β -lactoglobulin, K-casein

Soft corona

Band	kDa	Protein identified
1	30	α -S1-casein, α -S2-casein
2	28	β -casein
3	26	α -S1-casein, β -casein
4	21	β -casein, α -S1-casein
5	19	α -S1-casein, β -lactoglobulin
6	18	α -S1-casein, β -lactoglobulin
7	14	α -S1-casein, α -S2-casein, α -lactalbumin, K-casein, β -casein, β -lactoglobulin

Hard corona

Band	kDa	Protein identified
1	30	α -S1-casein, α -S2-casein
2	28	β -casein, α -S2-casein
3	20	β -casein, α -S1-casein
4	18	β -lactoglobulin, α -S1-casein
5	14	α -S1-casein, K-casein, α -lactalbumin, β -lactoglobulin
6	30	β -casein, α -S1-casein, α -S2-casein, β -lactoglobulin
7	28	β -casein, α -S1-casein, α -S2-casein, β -lactoglobulin

Fig. 5. Identification of proteins in selected bands after *in vitro* digestion of cow's milk with or without polypropylene microplastics (PP-MP, 63–100 μ m), oxidized PP-MP and agglomerated polypropylene nanoplastics (PP-NP). The figures show representative results of two separate experiments with similar results. The abbreviation Std stands for protein marker (kDa), C-MP for digestion of milk proteins only, while M, BK, SC, and HC stand for milk, bulk solution, soft corona, and hard corona, respectively. The numbers 5, 30, and 120 represent the digestion times (min), while the numbers 10, 50, and 100 represent the concentration of PP-NP in μ g/mL.

the results of the effect of PS-MP on pepsin digestion of milk (de Guzman et al., 2023). Due to the digestion conditions (37 $^{\circ}$ C and pH 5), some of these released peptides, particularly those from β -lactoglobulin, could have formed covalent linkages and pepsin-digestion-resistant oligomers, supporting its identification in bands of higher MW (1, 2, and 3) (Dave et al., 2016; Olsen et al., 2015; Loveday et al., 2014). Apart from this, fragments of caseins and β -lactoglobulin were also found in the lower MW bands (4 and 6), and this is an expected phenomenon during the digestion of cow's milk.

Unlike the proteins identified after 5 min of milk digestion (without PP-MP), the bands from soft (bands 1–3) and hard coronas (bands 1–3, 6 and 7) obtained after 30 and 120 min of digesting milk in the presence of pristine PP-MP, only contained isoforms of caseins α -S1, α -S2 and β without the presence of any molecules of β -lactoglobulin. This suggests

β -lactoglobulin dimers did not participate in the formation of PP-MP coronas. In the case of oxidized PP-MP, the β -lactoglobulin dimers were only found in band 3. This could be a result of increased surface plastic polarity showing a closer resemblance to the observations in the bulk solution of milk digestion in the absence of PP-MP. While β -lactoglobulin, the most abundant whey protein, was identified as the only protein in band 5 after 5 min of milk digestion without plastics, corresponding MW bands obtained in the soft and hard coronas also contained this undigested protein, which verified its participation in the formation of coronas. Previous studies have also established that β -lactoglobulin is resistant to pepsin cleavage (Hodgkinson et al., 2019). Additionally, α -lactalbumin was also identified in the soft and hard coronas of PP-MP. Due to the participation of caseins and β -lactoglobulin in the formation of hard corona, their hard corona epitopes were

Milk, pepsin and oxidized PP-MP

Milk, pepsin, and PP-NP

Fig. 5. (continued).

analyzed. Immunoglobulin E (IgE) epitopes associated with caseins, specifically α -S1-casein (95–208) and β -casein (185–224), were commonly found in the hard corona of both pristine and oxidized PP-MP. Additionally, β -lactoglobulin IgE epitopes in the regions 17–32 and 143–160 were identified (Fig. S4). These findings indicate that interactions with PP-MP could have induced conformational changes in these proteins, leading to the exposure of linear or conformational IgE-binding epitopes and an increase in allergenic potential in susceptible infants (Shi et al., 2024).

In milk samples digested in the presence of agglomerated PP-NP, lactadherin and serum albumin were identified in bands 1–3 and 4, respectively. These proteins play a pivotal role in infants by performing specific important biological functions necessary for their growth and health (Jeruzalska and Mazur, 2023; Jin et al., 2023; Layman et al., 2018). Considering that PP-NP agglomerates were not separated from the bulk solution, it is not possible to establish conclusions about the participation of these proteins in the formation of coronas.

At a molecular level, the participation of single proteins in the formation of a soft corona is still not fully understood, as are the effects of the soft corona. Although the soft corona has been reported to easily disintegrate (García-Álvarez and Vallet-Regí, 2021), the rate at which the proteins dissociate is still unknown, making it difficult to understand the fate of proteins. Therefore, a better understanding of the soft corona requires future investigations to extensively explore this area, especially using the physiological conditions of infants. Furthermore, investigations are still warranted for the hard corona, given that the formation of this corona is followed by conformational changes of proteins, which alter their capability for digestion, activity, and cellular function (Walkey and Chan, 2012). Given that milk proteins play a vital role in the growth of infants by supplying them with compounds needed to support their growth and development (Layman et al., 2018), further investigations of chronic effects of infant exposure to MNP through

formula feeding are urgently needed.

4. Conclusion

This study provides a detailed investigation on the impact of physiological conditions (pH and pepsin activity) and PP-MP on the digestion of cow's milk proteins in adults and infants. It further studied the effect of PP-MP oxidation and use of different concentrations of agglomerated PP-NP on the digestion of milk proteins in infants. This study is the first to report on the effect of PP-MP (pristine and oxidized) and agglomerated PP-NP on the rate and impact of cow's milk protein in an infant digestion model. We established that cow's milk protein digestion, either in the absence or presence of PP-MP, was much slower in infants than adults, showcasing the effect of variation in the physiological conditions between adults and infants. In addition, oxidation of the PP-MP significantly enriched some proteins in soft and hard corona in infants due to the changes in chemical and structural properties of the plastic. In the presence of agglomerated PP-NP the rate of protein digestion in infants is further decreased, largely affecting proteins such as β -lactoglobulin, a known allergen from cow's milk. Six different types of proteins, including casein α -S1, α -S2, β and K, β -lactoglobulin, and α -lactalbumin, contributed to the formation of soft and hard corona, and this suggests that their activity and biological functions are compromised. This study focused on the digestion of cow's milk; however, real food for infants such as infant formula should be investigated as the interaction of MP and NP with proteins in infants might be affected by the food matrix.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tafadzwa Kaseke: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Project administration, Methodology,

Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Vesna Jovanovic**: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Lukas Wimmer**: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Tamara Vasovic**: Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Tamara Mutic**: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Jelena Acimovic**: Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Lea Ann Dailey**: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources. **Tanja Cirkovic Velickovic**: Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix. ASupplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2025.126803>.

Data availability

The mass spectrometry proteomics data was deposited to the ProteomeXchange Consortium via the PRIDE [1] partner repository with the dataset identifier PXD057063 and 10.6019/PXD057063.

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